

Introducing the EMM Survey Registry!

A new tool for discovering and learning about quantitative surveys on the integration and inclusion of ethnic and migrant minorities (EMM)

The **EMM Survey Registry**—which has been co-created by **COST Action 16111 - ETHMIGSURVEYDATA**, the H2020 project **SSHOC**, and the ANR project **FAIRETHMIGQUANT**—is a **free online tool for discovering and learning about existing quantitative surveys undertaken with EMM (sub) populations** in Europe and beyond. This tool not only **brings together previously scattered information** about these surveys but also **offers detailed and structured metadata** for each of the surveys. **Designed with the end-users in mind**, this tool can also easily be leveraged by anyone interested in doing research or policy-related work using quantitative surveys on EMMs' integration and inclusion.

The EMM Survey Registry is **currently live and available in beta version**. This version is **fully functional and displays metadata about 900+ surveys from 22 different countries**. The tool has also already **welcomed 300-400 unique users each month** from all over the globe and from different disciplines, sectors, industries, etc. Moreover, it aspires to showcase survey research on EMMs in 30 European and neighbouring countries.

In the coming months, an **additional 100-200 surveys will be added** to the EMM Survey Registry covering additional countries. **Survey producers will also be invited to contribute their own metadata** (for free but with quality supervision) to help expand the metadata collection of the registry, as well as share their research with an international audience.

Quick statistics about the surveys included in the EMM Survey Registry

Number of surveys displayed
563 = national scope
343 = subnational scope

906

Number of different EMM groups identified across the surveys

164

Percentage of surveys covering ethnic minorities

42%

Percentage of surveys that are repeated cross-sectional or longitudinal

64%

Percentage of surveys for which the data is publicly available for re-use

33%

NOTE: The statistics are based on the metadata available on 18.03.2021

Creating a COVID-19 collection: contribute to the EMM Survey Registry

Since the start of the pandemic in 2020, a **growing number of COVID-19 surveys have been conducted with EMMs all across the world**, either targeting these minorities as the main focus of the survey or within general population surveys with boost samples. As these surveys can **provide meaningful insights about the COVID-19 experience for EMMs**, the EMM Survey Registry will be curating a special COVID-19 collection! We are calling on all the survey research community to contribute to this public resource that will make COVID-19 surveys covering the EMM populations findable and accessible.

If you are a **data producer who is currently developing or has already completed a COVID-19 survey that includes EMM respondents** (a sample of at least 250 individuals), you can contribute metadata about your survey directly to the EMM Survey Registry by following the steps below:

- **Send an email to sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr** with the subject line, "COVID-19 survey," to **express your interest** in contributing metadata about your survey. In the body of the email, please provide the name of your survey as well as some general information about your survey (country and locations where conducted, sample sizes, which minorities included, timing, etc.).
- **Fill out an [application form](#) to request an account** that will grant you access to an online form for contributing metadata.

Once **both of these steps have been completed, the administrators of the EMM Survey Registry will be in touch via email** to discuss the next steps.

Please note that you will **not be asked to add any micro-data or survey findings** to the EMM Survey Registry; you will only share information about the technical characteristics of the survey. If you have already made the data available in a repository or archive, you will be able to provide links to the deposited data or to any publications you wish to share with the public. For an **example of how a COVID-19 survey has been documented on the EMM Survey Registry** [click here](#).

All COVID-19 surveys that are captured on the EMM Survey Registry will have **their metadata publicly displayed**. These surveys will also be **searchable using the keyword 'COVID-19'**.

For any questions about the COVID-19 collection and/or the process for contributing metadata, please email the administrators of the EMM Survey Registry at sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr.

Questions and/or comments? Get in touch by emailing sshoc.project@sciencespo.fr
Want to learn more about the EMM Survey Registry? Check out the ETHMIGSURVEYDATA [Youtube channel](#) and [Zenodo community page](#)
Interested in ETHMIGSURVEYDATA and its work? Visit our website: <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/>

